

Organophosphonic Acids as Complexones Part—II : Interaction of Ethylenediphosphonic Acid with Some Divalent Metal Ions

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Reactions between bivalent metal ions [Mn(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II)] and ethylenediphosphonic acid (EDP) have been carried out in aqueous medium and the solid products, $M_nL_nH_nO$ ($n=0, 3$ or 4), have been characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, ir and electronic spectral and magnetic measurement data. Thermal stability of the compounds has also been studied.

PREPARATION of ethylenediphosphonic acid (EDP) from ethylene glycol and phosphorus trichloride has been reported¹. From the survey of the literature, it seems that no attempt has been made to use it as a complexing agent. In continuation of our work on organophosphonic acids², we report here the synthesis and structural studies of metal derivatives of ethylenediphosphonic acid. In the present investigation, reactions with bivalent metals, Mn(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pb(II), have been studied.

Experimental

Phosphorus trichloride and ethyleneglycol (B. D. H.) and bivalent metal acetates (B. D. H., AnalaR) were used as such.

Preparation of the ligand: Bis (ethylene) dihydrogenphosphite was prepared by the method of Cook *et al*³. It was then hydrolysed by adding calculated amount of water to give EDP. The product was purified by distilling it under reduced pressure (Found: P, 31.9, $C_2H_4P_2O_6$ requires P, 32.63%).

Preparation of metal derivatives: Aqueous solution of the acid (1 mole) was added to metal salt solution (2 mole) with constant stirring at room temperature. The precipitation was effected by dropwise addition of dilute ammonia solution. The precipitates were filtered and washed with distilled water and then dried at 50-60° till constant weight. They were neither soluble in water nor in any common organic solvent. They did not melt when heated even upto 300°. Elemental analysis using conventional methods⁴, and colour of the compounds have been given in Table 1.

IR spectra were taken in nujol ($600-4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) using KBr pellets on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Diffuse reflectance spectra in the region 200-1200 nm were run on a Unicam SP-700 spectrophotometer with a standard reflectance accessory using MgO as the reference. Magnetic measurements were made on Guoy's balance.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL STATE, ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Compound	Colour and state	Analysis				μ_{eff} B.M.
		%M		%P		
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
Mn ₂ EDP	White solid	37.4	37.1	20.9	20.9	3.85
Ni ₂ EDP.4H ₂ O	Light green solid	30.9	31.2	16.13	16.30	2.24
Zn ₂ EDP.3H ₂ O	White solid	34.06	34.9	15.90	16.7	—
Cd ₂ EDP.3H ₂ O	White solid	47.5	48.4	12.8	13.3	—
Pb ₂ EDP	White solid	70.0	69.0	10.4	10.3	—

Thermal analysis of the compounds was done in the atmosphere of air at National Chemical Laboratory, Poona. The specimens were heated at the rate of 10°/min in 20-1000° range and heated alumina was used as standard.

Results and Discussion

Reactions of metal acetates with ethylenediphosphonic acid in aqueous solution yield solid complexes of the general composition $M_nEDP.nH_2O$ where M is Mn(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) or Pb(II) and $n=0, 3$ or 4 . The structures of these compounds have been elucidated from the infrared, electronic spectral, magnetic measurements and thermogravimetric analytical studies.

The ir spectrum of the free acid shows peaks at 2420 and 1220 cm^{-1} which are characteristic of the P-H and P=O vibrations indicating that the phosphonate form is predominant in the free acid. However, in the ir spectra of metal derivatives phosphoryl frequencies disappear suggesting the formation of metal organophosphite. Formation of the phosphites is indicated from the elemental analysis also. This can be represented as follows:

Similar results have been reported when certain organophosphorus acids containing the P(O)(OH) group were converted to the silver or lead salts⁵⁻⁷.

Other absorption bands of EDP and its metal derivatives have been given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA FOR FREE LIGAND AND ITS DIFFERENT BIVALENT METAL DERIVATIVES

Assignments	EDP	Mn(II)	Ni(II)	Zn(II)	Cd(II)	Pb(II)
P=O	1220	—	—	—	—	—
P-H	2420	—	—	—	—	—
(P)-O-C	1090	1090(br)	1080(br)	1090(br)	1050(br)	1040(br)
P-O-(C)	1000	975	980	980	980(sh)	960(sh)

Thermal analysis: The general scheme of thermal decomposition is the same for all complexonates. Only the derivatogram of nickel(II) salt has therefore been given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Derivatogram of $Ni_2EDP.4H_2O$ (100 mg specimen).

The thermogravimetric curve for nickel(II) salt shows that it is stable upto 60° . When heated in the temperature range $60-225^\circ$, the total loss in mass is 16.5% and it corresponds to loss of 3 moles of water (theoretically reqd. loss = 16.4%). The absence of plateaux or inflections on mass loss curve indicates detachment of strictly determined number of molecules of water. This mass loss is accompanied by a broad endothermic effect with a minima at 140° . In the second stage of decomposition ($225-400^\circ$) two overlapping effects are observed which can be readily observed in DTG curve. By projection of minima of DTG curve onto the TG curve, the weight losses in two steps are 2.5% ($225-320^\circ$) and 3.0% respectively. The first one corresponds to the loss of the fourth water molecule (2.6% theoretical) and the second step seems to be the decomposition of organic part. DTA curve shows exothermic peak

with a maxima at 350° and has an inflection at 280° . Due to the fast rate of heating perhaps, two clearly separate peaks are not observed. On further heating in the range of $400-600^\circ$ there is a gradual loss in mass of the specimen amounting to $\sim 2\%$, showing absence of any stable intermediate. At 650° sharp exothermic peak is observed on DTA curve with slight mass gain.

Calculations show that the final products of thermal decomposition are probably metal oxide and P_2O_5 . Theoretical loss is 22.3%, experimental being 22.5%.

Electronic spectra and magnetic moments :

$Ni_2EDP.4H_2O$: The magnetic moment of the title compound at room temperature is 2.24 B. M. For octahedral nickel(II) complexes, magnetic moments lie usually within the range 2.9-3.3 B. M. whereas for tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes the moments ranging from 3.2 to 4.0 B. M. are anticipated depending upon distortion from the ideal T_d symmetry⁹. The anomalous magnetic moment in this case can be attributed to antiferromagnetic interactions.

Electronic spectra, however, permit an unambiguous structural assignment. The diffuse reflectance spectrum of nickel(II) complex shows three bands at 29410; 16670 and 10870 cm^{-1} which arise from the transitions for $^3A_{2g}$ ground state to the excited levels 3E_g (F), $^3T_{1g}$ (F) and $^3T_{2g}$ (P) in the order of increasing energy. ν_2 appears as a doublet which is ascribed to a gain in intensity of $^3A_{2g} \rightarrow ^1E_g$ transition through configurational interaction with the $^3T_{1g}$ (F) level¹⁰. The small magnitude of splitting of ν_1 (10630 and 10870 cm^{-1}) is indicative of lowering in symmetry from O_h to C_{2v}^{11} .

The value of Racah parameter from spin allowed transitions is 898 cm^{-1} , which is 86.3% of free ion value 1041 cm^{-1} and crystal field stabilization energy is 10,870 cm^{-1} .

Mn_2EDP : In the absence of solution spectra it is not possible to assign stereochemistry.

The magnetic moment value at room temperature (3.85 B. M.) lies between those expected for high spin and low spin d^5 octahedral complexes. This is proposed to be due to the presence of thermal equilibrium between spin state $S = \frac{1}{2}$ and $S = 5/2$ ⁶.

$Zn_2EDP.3H_2O$ and $Cd_2EDP.3H_2O$: As expected for d^{10} system, they are diamagnetic in nature.

An attempt to prepare Hg(II) salt resulted in its reduction to mercurous state, which on addition of excess ligand precipitates metallic mercury.

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